

Consumer Attitudes towards Single-Use Plastic & Policy Intervention

Rajiv Gupte¹, Anand Limaye²

Abstract

Single use plastic worldwide is increasing creating significant ecological, social and economic impact (Buckminster Fuller). In India, currently 11 Kg. plastic is consumed per capita per year, as compared to 36 Kg. in China (Lewis Retamal) This paper takes an account of extent of the problem and methodologies used by various countries to mitigate the issue. The researcher wishes to study whether the motivating factors are generally internalised, and integrated into the consumers cognitive and goal structures or just shallowing introjected social forum. Once the motivations are clearly understood then it would be relevant to study the ecologically conscious consumer and understand whether there are common values guiding environmentally desirable behaviour. Laddering technique is used to develop hierarchical value maps for Means Ends analysis. Means end theory suggests that there is a hierarchical organization of consumer perceptions and product knowledge (Young and Feign 1975, Gutman 1982) that range from attribute to consumption consequences to personal values (Attribution - Consequences - Values). This basis hierarchy starts with product attributes which have consumption, consequences. Each consequence in turn supports and or more importantly values in person's life. (Which Drucker has defined as applied behaviors Science). Based on the results, the paper examines, whether banning the plastic is the most optimum solution, or a balance between product ban, product replacement and improved waste collection can be considered. Ternary plotting of the approaches are discussed to devise appropriate policy intervention.

Keywords: Consumer attitude, Laddering Environment

¹Professor, MET Institute of Management, Mumbai
Email: rajivgupte1@rediffmail.com
²Professor, MET Institute of Management, Mumbai

Introduction

Since the 1950s, growth in the production of plastic has largely outpaced that of any other material, with a global shift from the production of durable plastics to single-use plastics (including packaging). The production of plastic is largely reliant on fossil hydrocarbons, which are non-renewable resources. If the growth in plastic production continues at the current rate, by 2050 the plastic industry may account for 20% of the world's total oil consumption.

Much has been said about the catastrophic effects due to usage of plastics, this article speaks about the public policy intervention needed.

National-level plastic bag bans and Styrofoam regulations

bans from developing countries, typically on plastic carrier bags, include the local "ban on delivery or purchasing of goods and materials in plastic wrappers or plastic bags in the state of Sikkim, India" in 1998 (Asia region); a national ban on "plastic bags <30 and a levy on retailer for thicker ones" in South Africa in 2003 (Africa region); and a local "ban on the use of polyethylene bags in Córdoba, Argentina" in 2009 (Central and South America region).

Recent announcements regarding restrictions at national level on a wider array of single-use plastics, include the proposed directive from the European Union to implement consumption reduction and market reduction measures on food containers, cups for beverages, cotton bud sticks, cutlery, plates, stirrers, straws and sticks for balloons, and to push for a 90% collection rate of single-use plastic bottles. The UK Government has outlined its intentions to "eliminate all avoidable plastic waste "by 2042 through various voluntary and regulatory interventions, in its recently published "A Green Future: Our 25 Year Plan to Improve the Environment". Perhaps the most ambitious national plan is that of India, where the Prime Minister has indicated his intent to eliminate all single-use plastic in the country by 2022. Bans on single-use plastics at city-level have also been implemented, or currently being planned by, amongst others, Montreal, Mumbai, New Delhi, Seattle and Vancouver.

This seems a tantalizingly straightforward idea, at the heart of which lies connections between economic development, environmental protection and social welfare; each element reinforcing the other. However, making these connections operational presents a significant challenge for a wide range of stakeholders including government, non-governmental organizations, business, community groups and individuals. This challenge is amplified further by sometimes competing perspectives as to what constitutes 'sustainable' development, contested evidence bases on the causal links of unsustainable development and complexities associated with aligning individual behaviour with this overarching objective of public policy (Blewitt, 2008). Despite these formidable challenges, there is growing consensus that production and consumption patterns need to be brought into alignment for the broader goal of sustainable development to be achieved (Jackson, 2006).

Historically, there has been little appetite for either legislative or taxation as preferred mechanism to modify consumer behaviour in relation to plastic bag use. Instead, voluntary action initiated from within the retail sector (underpinned by dialogue with the Government) and community initiatives have been to the fore in this regard.

The leakage of single-use plastic into the environment, and the resultant pressure from civil society has resulted in action by both government and business. Government has typically resorted to bans on single-use plastics, or economic instruments such as taxes. Some of the earliest

Business has also taken strides to reduce the negative impacts associated with products at end of life. At the World Economic Forum in Davos in January 2018, eleven global brand owners, retailers and packaging companies committed to making 100% of their packaging reusable, recyclable or compostable by 2025 or earlier. Companies included Amcor, Ecover, evian, L'Oréal, Mars, M&S, PepsiCo, The Coca-Cola Company, Unilever, Walmart and Werner & Mertz, with Nestlé joining the list in April 2018 and Colgate-Palmolive joining in June 2018. A number of global brand owner's were also amongst the 250+ companies that signed the New Plastics Economy Global Commitment, at the Our Ocean Conference in Bali

in October 2018. One of the aims of the Global Commitment being to "eliminate the plastic we don't need—the throwaway straws, cutlery and cups; unnecessary packaging and items that can be replaced with better alternatives".

With a strong drive to #BeatPlasticPollution, the United Nations Environment Programme has provided guidance on actions that the public, private sector entities and governments can take to minimise the production and use of single-use plastics. These include: (i) waste management system improvements, (ii) promotion of eco-friendly alternatives, (iii) social awareness and public pressure and (iv) voluntary reduction strategies and agreements.

As countries respond to the leakage of waste plastic into the environment, particularly our

means, competing, "solutions" are emerging in the global discourse—"ban it", "replace it", "close the tap". In other words, (i) ban single-use plastics, as many countries and cities are doing; (ii) replace petroleum-based single-use plastics with alternative bio-benign materials, such as paper, glass or biodegradable plastics; or (iii) improve waste collection coverage and send all collected waste to appropriate end-of-pipe treatment facilities, whether it be engineered landfills, or recycling or recovery centres, thereby ensuring that plastic has little opportunity to "leak" into the environment.

Here, the authors first analyse the consumer's attitude towards single use plastic.

This research seeks to study the factors which guide the environmentally desirable behaviour. The researcher wishes to study whether the motivating factors are generally internalised, and integrated into the consumers cognitive and goal structures or just swallowing introjected social forum.

Once the motivations are clearly understood then it would be relevant to study the ecologically conscious consumer and understand whether there are common values guiding environmentally desirable behaviour.

This will help in designing public policy for Sustainable Development.

Means end theory suggests that there is a hierarchical organisation of consumer perceptions and product knowledge (Young and Feigin 1975, Gutman 1982) that range from attribute to consumption consequences to personal values (Attribution - Consequences - Values). This basic hierarchy starts with product attributes which have consumption consequences. Each consequence in turn supports and or more importantly values in person's life. (Which Drucker has defined as Applied Behaviours Science)

(Reynolds, Geugler and Howard, 1995) Means end theory suggests that the concrete attributes link to self relevance and more abstract association.

Laddering is an effective method to evaluate and draw implications about the means end theory. Values are often attributed to deep emotional needs and represent real reasons why people buy /consume products.

In order to study motivating factors for ecologically concerned consumer. Laddering technique is used and is based on means end theory.

Hierarchically value maps are drawn and these maps help us analyse whether there are any consumer guiding environmentally desirable behaviour and whether these values are genuine internalised.

Attitudes

By definition, the ecologically concerned consumer's attitude must express concern for ecology (Kinnear, Taylor, and Ahmed 1974). The impact of ecological concern on consumption and voting behavior has frequently been assessed (Balderjahn 1988; Crosby, Gill, and Taylor 1981; Crosby and Taylor 1982, 1983; Henion 1976; Kassarjain 1971; Kinnear and Taylor 1973). Research indicates that ecological concern is related to, but is not highly correlated with consumption behavior. Additionally, attitude toward pollution has been found to affect one's attitude toward ecologically conscious living (Balderjahn 1988). This suggests that those who are genuinely concerned about pollution are inclined to take measures to circumvent further

The results from analysing consumer behaviour in the treatment and control shops show that the cash-back scheme was the most effective intervention and that it reduced plastic bag usage by 5.5%. The cloth bag and information schemes reduced plastic bag use by 4.5% and 3.5% respectively. Cumulatively, the three schemes increased the proportion of consumers bringing their own bags from 4.6% to 17.8%. On the other hand, plastic bag usage came down from 80.8% to 57.1%.

The study shows that information highlighting the environmental impacts of plastic bag usage can influence consumer behaviour. In other words, very low cost interventions can change consumer attitudes towards reusable bags. The study also shows that subsidies, either in cash or in kind (in the form of reusable bags) and explicit pricing could lead to lower plastic bag use. A comparison was made with studies conducted in other countries where similar interventions were introduced. The countries included Ireland where plastic bag use came down by 90% and China where it came down by 49%. These other studies suggest that the reduction in plastic bag use in the Delhi study was small, but it is possible that this gap might go down over a period of time.

POLICY INTERVENTION

Product Bans

If poorly implemented and enforced by government, such bans can have significant unintended consequences (e.g., where banned single-use plastic products are smuggled into the country, used, but end up with no end-of-life solution for safe disposal). Smuggling of plastic bags has been reported in many countries, including, in Africa, Cameroon, Rwanda and Kenya.

Product Replacement

The response typically adopted by business (e.g., brand owners and retailers), where they have little control over improving waste collection services, and no appetite for reducing product consumption, is to switch to alternative product designs or materials in an effort to reduce potential reputational damage from their products leaking into the environment.

With limited global success in plastic recycling—only 9% of all plastic produced has been

Conclusion

1. Consumers primarily buy/use plastic bags for convenience and cost
2. Intense motivation to comply with usage of paper/cloth is driven by "good civic" rather than environmental consciousness
3. Due to economic administrative reasons,
 - a. Product ban
 - b. Product replacement
 - c. Improved waste collection

All three methods' are to be used Depending upon the sector and regional nuances we recommend different approaches for different regions

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Environmental Marketing
 - M.J.Polonsky
 - Alma T. Mintu-Wimsatt
2. Innovative Marketing in Turbulence and
 - Prof. J.Patki, Prof. R. Sinha, Prof. C.Kaushik
3. Consumption Patterns and Buying Motives
 - J. Sauders, T. Ritchen
4. Consumer Values, relevant to adopting bio-tech foods
 - Susan Granthum
5. Consumer Motivation and Cognitive Structure Behind Food Purchasing
 - F.V.Christos, Maglava Ch. George, P.P. Anastatios
6. A Study On The Changing Attitudes Of Consumers Towards Green Products
 - Dr. M. Bhanumati
7. Green marketing Practices By Companies In India For Sustainable Marketing
 - C. Sentil Nathan
8. Green Marketing: Opportunity and Innovation in Turbulent Times
 - Rajesh Faldu
9. Ecological Imperatives and the Role of Marketing
 - Jagdish N. Seth, Atul Parnatiyar
10. Conserving Consumer: Implications for Public Policy Formation in Promoting Conservation Behaviour - Gregory M. Pickett, Norman Kaugun, Stephen J. Grove
11. Eco-Attitudes & Eco Behaviour - Scott D. Johnson, Denise M. Johnson
12. Ecologically Concerned Consumers and Their Product Purchases
 - T. Betting Cornwell
 - Charles H. Schwepker, Jr.
13. Implications of Understanding Basic Attitude Change Processes and Attitude Structure for Enhanced Pro-Environmental Behaviour
 - Stephen M. Smith
 - Curtis P. hangtvedt
14. Adams, Richard (1990), "The Greening of Consumerism," *Accountancy*, June, 81-82.
15. Aldenderfer, Mark S. and Roger K. Blashfield (1984). *Cluser Analysis*, Beverly Hills, CA: Sage Publications.
16. Bryson, Phillip J. (1984), *The Consumer Under Socialist Planning*, New York: Praeger.
17. Burant, Stephen R. (1988), *East Germany: A Country Study*, Washington D.C.: U.S. Government Printing Office.
18. Bush, Keith (1974), "The Soviet Response to Environmental Disruption," in *Environmental Deterioration in the Soviet Union and Eastern Europe*, New York: Praeger Publishers, 8-36.
19. Cezeaux, Andrea (1991), "East Meets West to Look for Toxic Waste Sites," *Science*, Vol. 251, 620-621.
20. Davis, Joel J. (1991), "A Blueprint for Green Marketing," *The Journal of Business Strategy*, July / August, 14-17.
21. Eisenhart, Tom (1991) "Energy Report: Out of Crisis Comes Opportunity," *Business Marketing*, May, T1-T8.
22. French, Hilary F. (1990), "Clearing the Air: A Global Agenda," *Columbia Journal of World Business*, Spring / Summer, 64-81.
23. Hair, Joseph F. Jr., Rolph E. Anderson, Ronald L. Tatham, and William C. Black (1992), *Multivariate Data Analysis*, Third Edition, New York : Macmillan Publishing Company.
24. Hardy, Ed (1990), "Eco-Entrepreneurs," *American Demographics*, July, 49-50.
25. Henzler, Herbert (1992), "Managing the Merger: A Strategy for the New Germany," *Harvard Business Review*, January-February, 24-29.
26. Jay, Leslie (1990), "Markets Discover the Eco-Consumer," *Management Review*, June, 24-